

DYSPHEMISM AND ASSOCIATED PHENOMENA

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Abstract: This study delves into dysphemisms—a relatively underexplored linguistic phenomenon characterized by the use of words or expressions with intentionally negative connotations. By comparing and contrasting dysphemisms with euphemisms, the research illuminates their distinct roles in communication, societal dynamics, and cultural expressions.

Key words: x-phemism, dysphemism, euphemism, cacophemism, slang, vulgarism.

According to Rezanova's description, the early 21st century is characterized by an increase in the level of negativity in conversational communication, a situation acknowledged by both sociologists and linguists. This phenomenon is attributed to the polarization of society, conflicts between government and public interests, and clashes among various ethnic and social groups. Through the analysis of statements about politics, researchers have been able to examine how political figures and their actions are perceived in the public consciousness. Such in-depth analysis has been facilitated by concepts such as euphemism and dysphemism. Dysphemisms, similar to euphemisms, have not been widely covered in Uzbek linguistic literature. There are hardly any works that study dysphemisms in the Uzbek language or compare them with those in English. The concept was first somewhat discussed in the 1983 publication "Stylistics of the Uzbek Language." In Uzbek linguistics, works dedicated to euphemism, such as the candidate dissertations of N. Ismatullayeva, the candidate and doctoral dissertations of A. Omonturdiyev, and the candidate dissertations of X. Qodirova, Sh. Gulyamova, and D. Rustamova, do not possess a comparative nature.

When discussing the emergence and historical development of dysphemism, it's crucial to provide information about the motives contributing to verbal aggression, which lead to the occurrence of this phenomenon. According to Rezanova, these motives can be divided into three major groups:

1. The speaker's negative communicative intention, aimed at inflicting communicative harm on the interlocutor;
2. The recipient's negative emotional reactions to a certain statement (such as resentment, anger, irritation, etc.) and the types of response statements they provoke (accusations, opposition, disagreement, etc.);
3. The lack of congruence in the form and/or content of the statement with the character of verbal interaction and the "dignity of the recipient." For example, personal addresses, insulting words, or gestures directed at an opponent in a formal environment, and so forth.

Additionally, in the book "Euphemism and Dysphemism: Language Used As Shield and Weapon" by Allan & Burrige, reasons for using dysphemisms are provided, which extend beyond the above-mentioned motives to include several situations:

1. Expressing surprise or astonishment. The function of dysphemism in expressing surprise or astonishment involves conveying a strong sense of wonder, shock, or disbelief, often achieved through exaggeration or extreme terms.
2. Demonstrating closeness in friendship. Dysphemism contributes to creating intimacy and informality, thereby strengthening bonds among friends. For instance, a group of girls might use dysphemism examples humorously among themselves to affirm their strong friendship and the notion that such words cannot break their bond.
3. Depicting the collective identity of a group. Dysphemism aids in illustrating the collective identity of a group, enhancing the sense of mutual understanding and unity among its members, typically through inside jokes or special terms. For example, a team might use special nicknames or terms to foster a sense of connection and closeness among its members, or to denigrate or disparage people or

opposing views outside the group, thereby establishing a clear group identity. For instance, a group of sports fans might refer to the fans of rival teams as "losers" or "cheaters" to emphasize their own group's loyalty and superiority.

Dysphemism in speech means the use of units with negative connotations, but this does not imply their absence in literary language. On the contrary, these units are used to leave an intensified negative impression on the listener about an event or person.

Classification of Dysphemisms (According to Rezanova): A) Dysphemisms related to death, illness, physical, and moral defects; B) Dysphemisms associated with a wide range of criminal groups; C) Dysphemisms related to human flaws; D) Dysphemisms related to ethnic affiliations; E) Dysphemisms with religious content.

Types of Dysphemism (According to Allan & Burrige): F) Synecdoche – Used to describe something in its entirety. G) Dysphemistic epithets – Use of animal names, for example, “pig”, “dog”, “rat”, or “snake”. H) Euphemistic dysphemism – A softer expression is used without insulting. I) Dysphemistic euphemism – Used humorously among close friends without any hostility. J) “-ist” dysphemism – Directed at a specific ethnic group. L) Name dysphemism – Choosing a simpler or lower style in addressing someone, replacing a relative's title with their name, indicating the speaker opts for a more casual or lower style in the social context. "What are you doing, John?" (Instead of "Dad"/"Father") "How are you, Bill?" (Instead of "Uncle") Many languages, more so than English, express respect through verb tenses (for example, the respect suffix “siz”, “lar” in Uzbek), thus making it more likely to inadvertently use name dysphemisms. Therefore, caution is needed in translation to avoid accidentally insulting the speakers. However, in some cases, if the listener prefers being called by their name, as opposed to “dad, mom”, in modern families or due to cultural backgrounds, such instances are not considered dysphemism. Similarly, being more formal than expected can also be a type of dysphemism. For example, if a child usually calls their father "dad" or "papa", using the more formal "father" could imply distance and could be seen as an insult. Likewise, calling a child by their full name instead of a nickname could be

considered dysphemism. The speaker might need to use a name dysphemism or address dysphemism to express anger or dissatisfaction towards an individual or a group of people. M) Non-verbal dysphemism – Used to insult someone through gestures. N) Cross-cultural dysphemism – Various slang terms are used as dysphemisms in one culture; on the other hand, they may have a completely different meaning in other cultures.

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